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Systematic design of absorption CO₂ processes considering total CO₂ avoided cost and varying operating conditions

Cristina Zotică^{a,*}, Chao Fu^a, Luca Riboldi^a, Simon Roussanaly^a, Rahul Anantharaman^a

^aSINTEF Energy Research, Trondheim 7036, Norway

Abstract

This work introduces a systematic design procedure for CO₂ absorption-based processes using as solvent the mixture of AMP-PZ. We propose to minimize the total CO₂ avoided cost. We make the assumption that the capture plant is retrofitted to an existing industrial plant whose operation and production are not changed. Under this assumption, we can define the total CO₂ avoided cost by using a method which considers the discounted cash flow resulted from implementing the capture unit. We consider a standard absorber-desorber process configuration, and we model the process in AspenPlus[®]. We systematically identify the degrees of freedom available for design, and we divided these into degrees of freedom used internally in the simulation in a Design-Specification block (e.g., solvent flowrate and reboiler duty), and degrees of freedom available to an external derivative-free optimizer (e.g., absorber packing height, AMP and PZ composition, and lean solvent loading). As a case study we consider a Waste-to-Energy plant.

Keywords: Absorption; CO₂ capture; systematic design; total CO₂ avoided cost; waste-to-energy

1. Introduction

Capture of CO₂ represents a powerful technology to decarbonize industrial plants with limited alternatives such as cement, waste-incineration or metal production and processing. Reactive absorption in aqueous amine solutions is a mature technology to capture CO₂ produced in industrial processes. One of its key advantages compared to other CO₂ capture technologies is that it yields a high purity by design. To be cost effective, solvent-based absorption CO₂ capture processes need to be optimally designed and operated. However, considering the complexity of these processes, this is not an easy task. Recent literature studies propose methodologies to optimize the design and operation for chilled ammonia process [1] or methyl-diethanolamine (MDEA) absorption-based CO₂ [2]. However, the mixtures of two amines, amino-methyl-propanol (AMP) and piperazine (PZ) has recently been proposed as the new benchmark solvent technology [3]. Therefore, in this work we use AMP-PZ as the solvent for the capture process.

One alternative for designing absorption-based CO₂ processes is to first optimize the technical performance, followed by evaluating the cost, see for example the work by [4]. Another approach is to consider process and/or economic heuristics to find a trade-off between operating costs (OPEX) and investments cost (CAPEX). For example, the OPEX is often approximated to the reboiler duty, while the CAPEX is often approximated by the cost associated

* Corresponding author. Email *address*: cristina.zotica@sintef.no

with the absorber, which is related to the absorber packing height, and a sensitivity analysis is performed to determine a good balance between the two. This analysis normally sets arbitrary criteria, for instance the rate of change of the specific reboiler duty (i.e., energy used to remove 1 kg of CO₂), to determine the design space to explore by varying parameters such as solvent loading, solvent cyclic capacity (i.e., difference between lean and rich amine CO₂ content), and absorber height. Certain constraints are also included, such as the minimum CO₂ capture rate, to screen out unfeasible designs. While these are reasonable approximations to reduce the computational efforts, they may not result in the optimal design of the process. Therefore, the objective of this work is to propose a systematic method for designing absorption CO₂ capture plants using an integrated process and cost analysis.

2. Modelling of the CO₂ absorption process

Fig.1 illustrates the process flowsheet for the reactive amine absorption CO₂ process that we consider. This is a standard absorber-stripper process configuration. The flue gas rich in CO₂ (stream 1) is first cooled with water in a direct contact cooler (DCC) before it enters the bottom of the absorber column. Here it flows counter currently with the solvent flow in which it physically dissolves and reacts with the amines. Before being released to the atmosphere, the sweetened gas is passed through a water-wash section at the top of the absorber column to remove part of the amines entrapped in the gas phase. If the temperature of the gas leaving the absorber column is too low, the gas may not have enough buoyancy and a heat exchanger may be used to increase the temperature by exchanging heat with the hot flue gas entering the process. The CO₂ rich solvent (stream 7) is first heated in a heat exchanger with the lean solvent leaving the stripper to recover heat and then sent to the top of the stripper (desorber column). Here the steam generated in a reboiler helps regenerate the solvent and produce purified CO₂. The purified CO₂ leaves the top of the stripper to be sent to the next processing step (note that we do not include the conditioning stage, and this is an outlet boundary in this work). The lean amine solvent is recycled to the absorber column. A thermal reclaimer is included to remove impurities (salts) thus purifying the solvent.

Fig.1. Process flowsheet of the CO₂ capture plant. Adopted from [5]

2.1. Modelling using AspenPlus®

We consider a standard absorber-stripper configuration as the basic process and implement in the simulation software Aspen-Plus®. To model the absorption process, we use rate-based modelling which is known to predict with a high accuracy the composition of the gas-phase, the solvent loading, as well as the absorber temperature profile compared to equilibrium models [6]. We use eNRTL property method to model the formation of electrolytes in the liquid streams and Redlich-Kwong equation of state. The interaction coefficients of these methods are taken from the work by [7]. To model the chemical reactions, we use the equilibrium constants and kinetic parameters provided by the work of [8], as well as data from AspenPlus® examples library.

3. Methodology for systematic design of CO₂ absorption processes

We define the design objective as to minimize the total CO₂ avoided cost by using the available degrees of freedom for design, while satisfying a set of constraints given by process specifications and environment regulations.

3.1. Defining the objective function: total avoided CO₂ cost

We start by defining the objective function. The total CO₂ avoided cost (CAC) is a single metric that encompasses both the operating and capital costs and it represents, as the name suggests, the cost of avoiding a unit of CO₂ emissions. We make the assumption that the capture plant is retrofitted to an existing industrial plant whose operation and production are not changed. Under this assumption, we can define the total CO₂ avoided cost by using a method which considers the discounted cash flow resulted from implementing the capture unit. This is calculated as the total annualized cost of implementing CCS divided by the annualized emission avoided ($m_{CO_2,avoided,y}$) (see Eq. 1 [9]). The total annualized cost is the sum of the annualized investment cost of the CO₂ capture unit (C_{inv}) (CAPEX), and the OPEX, e.g., the sum of the fuel cost (C_{fuel}), of the raw material costs (C_{RM}), the electricity cost (C_{el}) and of the other operation and maintenance costs ($C_{O\&M}$).

$$CAC = \frac{C_{inv} + C_{fuel} + C_{RM} + C_{O\&M}}{m_{CO_2,avoided,y}} \left[\frac{\text{€}}{\text{tCO}_2} \right] \quad (1)$$

where each cost is calculated as follows:

$$C_{inv} = \frac{\sum_i \frac{\text{Total Cost}(i)}{(1+d)^i}}{\sum_i \frac{1}{(1+d)^i}} \quad (2)$$

$$C_{fuel} = p_{bioCH_4} q_{heat} \text{ [€]} \quad (3)$$

$$C_{RM} = p_{RM} q_{RM} \text{ [€]} \quad (4)$$

$$C_{el} = p_{el} q_{el} \text{ [€]} \quad (5)$$

$$C_{O\&M} = 2.5\% \text{ [€]} \quad (6)$$

With p being the price in €/MWh or €/t, q the duty in MWh or the mass in t, $d = 10\%$ is the discount rate, and assuming that the construction costs in Eq. 2 are shared over 4-year construction period following a 20/30/30/20 allocation, and that the operating life of CO₂ capture plant is 25 years. We consider 8400 operating hours per year. Note that in this work we adopt a higher discount rate, compared to the conventional 8%, to reflect pseudo FOAK conditions [10].

In this work, we employ a pseudo first-of-a-kind (FOAK) approach to estimate the total cost of the capture plant. This approach is relevant for technologies in the early stage of commercialization [8,9], such as the case study presented (see Section 4). The alternative is Nth-of-a-kind to which is representative to more mature technologies thus not relevant in this work.

In this work, the capital cost of each operation unit (e.g., column, heat exchanger, pump, fan or duct) is computed using in-house polynomial functions that estimate direct costs of each component of the process combined with a factor-based cost escalation approach as in [11]. The cost functions were regressed from evaluation based on Aspen

Process Economic Analyzer[®] over a wide range of relevant conditions. These cost functions use as input process data extracted from the simulation in Aspen Plus[®]. For example, the heat exchanger, pump and fan costs are calculated using the duty of each equipment, while the columns cost is calculated as a function of the packing height. It is important here to note the assumptions and simplifications made to determine the columns cost functions. For the absorber, we consider given flue gas volumetric flowrate specific from the case study in Section 4 and a fixed diameter determined *a-priori* of solving the design optimization problem. Therefore, the absorber column cost is case specific. A similar approach has been used before in the literature (e.g., [12]).

In addition, we assume that the required process heat is generated by burning bio-methane, thus there is no additional CO₂ with fossil origin is generated. The required electric power is taken from the internal production. Note that the electricity consumption of the capture plant is small, and we make the assumption that it will not considerably affect the revenue of the WtE plant from selling electricity. Thus, the CO₂ avoided is equal to the CO₂ captured.

3.2. Identifying the degrees of freedom (DOF) available for design

To simplify the design procedure, we fix the geometry of the water-wash and stripper column, and it is the goal of future work to extend this design procedure to include these variables as degrees of freedom. The available degrees of freedom are:

- D1:** Solvent composition, i.e., mass concentration of AMP and PZ
- D2:** Lean solvent loading, i.e., mass concentration of CO₂
- D3:** Absorber packing height
- D4:** Reboiler heat duty (q_{heat})

In this work, D4 is computed internally in the simulation by using a Design-Specification block that manipulates the boil-up ratio such that the CO₂ capture ratio constraint is active (C1, see Section 3.3). Note that the solvent flowrate cannot be set freely, and it is given by **D1**, D2, C1 and the mass balance. Similarly to D4, the solvent flow is calculated using a Design-Specification block, that manipulates the solvent flow (with given **D1** and D2), such that C1 is satisfied. Therefore, the degrees of freedom for the external optimizer are **D1**, D2 and D3.

3.3. Identifying the process constraints

The process constraints are related to product specification (i.e., the CO₂ capture rate), environmental constraints or equipment specification (i.e., pressure drop, and minimum approach temperature). These are:

- C1:** CO₂ capture rate $\geq 90\%$
- C2:** Maximum available heat at the industrial plant
- C3:** Amine concentration in the sweetened gas $\leq 20\text{ mg/Nm}^3$
- C4:** Minimum pinch point difference for heat exchangers = $10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$
- C5:** Column diameter $< 12\text{ m}$
- C6:** Column pressure drop $< 5\text{ mbar}$
- C7:** Model equations (e.g., mass and energy balances, thermodynamic properties, equilibrium constants for reactions, electrolyte chemistry etc.)

Constraints C1, C3, C4, C7 are handled internally by AspenPlus[®]. Note that in this work we assume C1 to be an active constraint. The CO₂ purity is not given as a constraint because first, the absorption process inherently results in a high purity by design and second, we fix the condenser temperature and pressure and therefore there is no degree of freedom left to control the CO₂ concentration.

3.4. Defining fixed variables (parameters)

The next step is to define the parameters that are constant in the simulations. These are:

- P1:** Inlet boundary conditions, e.g., flue gas composition, flowrate, temperature, pressure
- P2:** Outlet boundary condition, e.g., captured CO₂ temperature, pressure

- P3:** Available cooling water temperature
P4: Price of utilities (e.g., solvent make-up, process water, cooling water, electricity, heat)
P5: Diameter of absorber column and geometry of the stripper, water-wash and DCC columns

Note that in this work **P5** is given as a parameter to reduce the number of degrees of freedom and simplify the optimization problem, but the goal is to include these as degrees of freedom in future work.

3.5. Optimization tool

To solve the optimal design problem, we choose to use an external optimizer instead of the build-in optimization tools Aspen-Plus® which are not always robust. However, the model in Aspen-Plus® is a black-box, meaning that we do not have access to the model equations and cannot obtain analytical derivatives or sensitivity value to use a gradient-based optimizer. Therefore, we use a derivative-free optimizer, and we select *Particle Swarm Optimization* (PSO) because it is easier to implement (i.e., less tuning parameters) compared to other methods in its class (e.g., genetic algorithm). It also has the potential of being parallelized. PSO explores the state space by sampling several N points (particles) and computing their respective objective function. In addition to a position in the state-space, the particles also have a velocity (rate and direction) which sets their next position in the state-space, where the objective function is again computed. The velocity is updated at each iteration, such that the particles move fast through the state space initially, but as a region appears to be most promising, the particles slowly move towards the global best. This is iteratively repeated until a certain criterion has been met, e.g., all particles have reached a consensus, or the maximum number of iterations has been reached, see [13]. The number of particles and the initial velocity are tuning parameters of the algorithm. To implement PSO we adapt the publicly available code from [14] and automate running Aspen-Plus via the COM interface in Python 3.

4. Case study: KVA Linth Waste-to-Energy plant

We apply the model described in Section 2 and the methodology described in Section 3 to design a CO₂ capture plant for the KVA Linth Waste-to-Energy plant which is a case study in the ACCSESS project [15,16]. The primal objective of the plant is to dispose of waste through incineration, and heat and electricity are byproducts of the process.

The necessary parameters (**P1** to **P5** from above), such as the flue gas data, but also the fixed geometry of the absorber and stripper are given in Table 1. Note that the flue gas from the plant is already cooled to the absorber operating temperature, and therefore a DCC is not necessary.

Table 1. Parameters for the Waste-to-Energy plant

Parameter	Unit	Value
Total flue gas flowrate	Nm ³ /h	74496
Pressure flue gas	bara	1.01
Temperature flue gas	°C	35
CO ₂ (wet basis)	vol % _{STP}	12.2
N ₂ (wet basis)	vol % _{STP}	77.4
O ₂ (wet basis)	vol % _{STP}	5.7
Pressure CO ₂ to conditioning	bara	2
Temperature CO ₂ to conditioning	°C	28
Available cooling water temperature	°C	18
Price AMP	€/kg	8
Price PZ	€/kg	6
Price cooling water	€/m ³	0.039
Price electricity	€/kWh	0.0688
Price heat (bioCH ₄)	€/GJ	13
Absorber diameter	m	4

Water wash diameter	m	4
Water wash packing height	m	4
Stripper diameter	m	4
Stripper packing height	m	9

Note that the prices in Table 2 are assumed to be constant throughout the operating life of the capture plant. Note that the electricity price in Table 2 is lower than the present levels and it does not reflect the current energy market outlook. However, the electricity usage of the capture process is relatively small and an increase in electricity prices is not expected to significantly change the operating costs.

Fig. 2 shows an example of the initial particles positions for **D1**, D2 and D3. These 30 points are obtained randomly using LHS (latin hypercube sampling). The initial velocity of the particles is randomly chosen between 0% and 25% in magnitude in each direction, and the particles position is updated according to the default PSO tuning parameters.

Fig. 2. Initial randomized particles positions

The resulted values for the degrees of freedom and shown in Table 2. The show that a lower cost of CO₂ avoided can be achieved at lower absorber packing height, but higher concentrations of AMP and PZ.

Table 2. Results for **D1**, D2 and D3.

Parameter	Unit	Value
Absorber packing height	m	8
AMP	wt%	32,5
PZ	wt%	15
CO ₂ lean solvent	wt%	5

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, we propose a systematic design procedure for CO₂ absorption processes where the solvent is the mixture of AMP-PZ. To model the process, we use rigorous rate-based modelling in AspenPlus®. The process design objective is to minimize the total CO₂ avoided cost (Eq. 1) calculated using a first of a kind cost methodology. The available degrees of freedom for the external optimizer (PSO) are the absorber packing height, lean solvent loading, concentration of AMP and concentration of PZ, while the reboiler duty and lean solvent flow is determined internally using a design-specification block such that the CO₂ capture rate is 90%. The results show that a lower cost can be achieved by reducing the absorber packing height and increasing the concentration of AMP and PZ. To further develop this work, we plan to consider three other industrial case studies [16], which allow us to analyze a wide range of flue gas characteristics such as composition and flowrate, as well as the various heat supply strategies that the plants may have. Furthermore, we plan to analyze the effect of increasing the CO₂ capture rate on the total avoided cost.

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